

Triple Connected Roman Domination Number on Some Particular Graphs

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Subject Classification number: 05C40, 05C69, 05C70

Abstract:- On a graph G , we can define a Roman domination function $f:V \rightarrow \{0,1,2\}$ satisfying the condition that every vertex $u \in V$ for which $f(u) = 0$ is adjacent to at least one vertex $v \in V$ for which $f(v) = 2$. The weight of a Roman dominating function is the value $f(v) = \sum_{v \in V} f(v)$. The Roman domination number $\gamma_R(G)$ is the minimum weight of a Roman dominating function on G . In a Roman dominating function if the induced subgraph $\langle V_1 \cup V_2 \rangle$ or $\langle V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected, then the Roman dominating function is called triple connected Roman dominating function (TCRDF). In this paper, we determine triple connected Roman domination number for triangle snake graph T_n , double triangle snake graph $D(T_n)$, Cartesian product $C_n \square P_n$, and Moser spindle graph.

Keywords:- Connected graphs, Triple connected graphs, Domination number, Roman domination number and Connected Roman domination number.

A. Definition: Triangular snake Graph

The triangular snake graph T_n is obtained from the path P_n by replacing each edge of the path by a triangle C_3 .

Example:

Fig. 1: Triangular snake graph T_5

B. Definition: Double Triangular snake Graph

The double triangular snake graph $D(T_n)$ consist of two triangular snakes that have a common path.

Example:

Fig. 2: Double triangular snake graph $D(T_4)$

I. INTRODUCTION

A subset S of $V(G)$ in G is called a dominating set, if and only if $N[S] = V(G)$. The domination number $\gamma(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of a dominating set of G . If S is a subset of $V(G)$, then we denote by $\langle S \rangle$, the subgraph induced by S . For notation and graph theory terminology in general, we follow [2]. The triple connected Roman domination number $\gamma_{TRC}(G)$ is the minimum weight of a triple connected Roman dominating function (TCRDF) on G , also we have $\gamma_{TRC}(G) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$

II. RESULT

In this Section we found the triple connected Roman domination number for triangle snake graph T_n , double triangle snake graph $D(T_n)$, Cartesian product $C_n \square P_n$, and Moser spindle graph.

• Theorem

The triple connected Roman domination number for any triangular snake graph T_n

$$\text{is } \gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{3n-5}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd, } n \geq 5 \\ \frac{3n-4}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even, } n \geq 6 \end{cases}$$

• Proof:

Let G be a triangular snake graph T_n

The triangular snake consists of u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1} vertices in the top of triangle and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n vertices at the bottom of the triangle. So, $V(G) = \{u_i, v_j : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{v_i u_i, u_i v_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$.

Now $V_2 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$, $V_1 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-2}\}$ and $V_0 = \{v_1, v_2, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1}\}$

Clearly, V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $\langle V_1 \cup V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected.

Hence the function $f = (V_0, V_1, V_2)$ is a triple connected Roman dominating function on G .

Case(i): If n is odd, $n \geq 5$, then we have $\gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$

Here $|V_1| = \frac{n-1}{2} - 1$, $|V_2| = \frac{n-1}{2}$

$$\gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = \frac{n-1}{2} - 1 + 2\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = \frac{3n-5}{5}$$

Case (ii): If n is even $n \geq 6$, then

Here $|V_1| = \frac{n}{2} - 2$, $|V_2| = \frac{n}{2}$

$$\gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = \frac{n}{2} + 2\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC}(T_n) = \frac{3n-4}{5}$$

• Theorem

The triple connected Roman domination number for a double triangular snake graph $D(T_n)$

$$\text{is } \gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{3n-5}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd, } n \geq 5 \\ \frac{3n-4}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even, } n \geq 6 \end{cases}$$

• Proof:

Let G be a double triangular snake graph $D(T_n)$

The graph $D(T_n)$ consists of u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1} vertices in the top triangle, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{n-1} are vertices in the bottom triangle and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n vertices at the common path of the double triangle. So, $V(G) = \{u_i, v_j, w_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and

$$E(G) = \{v_i u_i, u_i v_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1}, v_i w_i, w_i v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}.$$

Now $V_2 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$, $V_1 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-2}\}$ and $V_0 = \{v_1, v_2, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1}, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{n-1}\}$

Clearly, V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $\langle V_1 \cup V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected.

Hence the function $f = (V_0, V_1, V_2)$ is a triple connected Roman dominating function on G .

Case (i): If n is odd, $n \geq 5$, then we have $\gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$

Here $|V_1| = \frac{n-1}{2} - 1$, $|V_2| = \frac{n-1}{2}$

$$\gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = \frac{n-1}{2} - 1 + 2\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = \frac{3n-5}{5}$$

Case (ii): If n is even $n \geq 6$, then

Here $|V_1| = \frac{n}{2} - 2$, $|V_2| = \frac{n}{2}$

$$\gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = \frac{n}{2} + 2\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = \frac{3n-4}{5}$$

C. Definition: Cartesian product of graphs

The **Cartesian product** $G \square H$ of graphs G and H is a graph such that, the vertex set of $G \square H$ is the Cartesian product $V(G) \times V(H)$; and two vertices (u, u') and (v, v') are adjacent in $G \square H$ if and only if either $u = v$ and u' is adjacent to v' in H , or $u = v$ and u is adjacent to v in G .

• Theorem

The triple connected Roman domination number for Cartesian product $C_n \square P_n$

$$\text{is } \gamma_{TRC}(G) = \begin{cases} 6, & \text{if } n = 3 \\ (2i+1)(3i+1) + i, & \text{if } n = 3i+1, i \geq 1 \\ 2i(3i-1) + i - 1, & \text{if } n = 3i-1, i \geq 2 \\ 2i(3i) + i - 1, & \text{if } n = 3i, i \geq 2 \end{cases}$$

• Proof:

Let G be a Cartesian product $C_n \square P_n$ graph

The graph $C_n \square P_n$ consists of $V(G)$ as a vertex set and $E(G)$ as a edge set

$$\text{So, } V(G) = \{u_i, u'_i, v_i, v'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \text{ and}$$

$$E(G) = \begin{cases} \text{either } u_i = v_i \text{ and } u'_i \text{ is adjacent to } v'_i \text{ in } P_n, \\ \text{or } u'_i = v'_i \text{ and } u_i \text{ is adjacent to } v_i \text{ in } C_n, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n \end{cases}$$

Case (i): If $n = 3$, then we have $\gamma_{TRC} = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$

Fig. 3: Cartesian product $C_3 \square P_3$ graph

Clearly, V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $\langle V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected.

Hence the function $f = (V_0, V_1, V_2)$ is a triple connected Roman dominating function on G .

Here $|V_1| = 0, |V_2| = 3$

$$\gamma_{TRC} = 0 + 2(3) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC} = 6$$

Case (ii): If $n = 4$, then we have $|V_1| = 5, |V_2| = 4,$
 $\gamma_{TRC} = 5 + 2(4) = 3(4) + 1 = 13$
 $\Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC} = 13$

Fig. 4: Cartesian product $C_4 \square P_4$ graph

Similarly, if $n = 7,$ (n will be increased by 3 in each case)

We get $|V_1| = 9, |V_2| = 14, \gamma_{TRC} = 9 + 2(14) = 5(7) + 2 = 37$

For $n = 10,$ we have $|V_1| = 15, |V_2| = 29, \gamma_{TRC} = 15 + 2(29) = 7(10) + 3 = 73$

The following table gives the triple Roman domination number for the cartesian product upto n values.

S.No	The value of n	TCRDN
1	4	$\gamma_{TRC} = 3(4) + 1$
2	7	$\gamma_{TRC} = 5(7) + 2$
3	10	$\gamma_{TRC} = 7(10) + 3$
4	13	$\gamma_{TRC} = 9(13) + 4$
5	16	$\gamma_{TRC} = 11(16) + 5$
6	19	$\gamma_{TRC} = 13(19) + 6$
7	22	$\gamma_{TRC} = 15(22) + 7$
8	25	$\gamma_{TRC} = 17(25) + 8$
9	28	$\gamma_{TRC} = 19(28) + 9$
10	31	$\gamma_{TRC} = 21(31) + 10$
	.	
	.	
	.	
	.	
n	$n = 3i + 1, i \geq 1$	$\gamma_{TRC} = (2i + 1)(3i + 1) + i$

Table 1: Triple connected Roman domination numbers

In each case V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $\langle V_1 \cup V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected.

If $n = 3i + 1, i \geq 1,$ then we have the triple connected Roman domination number as

$$\gamma_{TRC} = (2i + 1)(3i + 1) + i = 6i^2 + 6i + 1$$

Case (iii): If $n = 5,$ then we have $|V_1| = 1, |V_2| = 10, \gamma_{TRC} = 1 + 2(10) = 4(5) + 1 = 21$

Fig. 5: Cartesian product $C_5 \square P_5$ graph

$\Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC} = 21$

Similarly, if $n = 8$, (n will be increased by 3 in each case)

We get $|V_1| = 4, |V_2| = 23, \gamma_{TRC} = 4 + 2(23) = 6(8) + 2 = 50$

For $n = 11$, we have $|V_1| = 7, |V_2| = 42, \gamma_{TRC} = 7 + 2(42) = 8(11) + 3 = 91$

S.No	The value of n	TCRDN
1	5	$\gamma_{TRC} = 4(5) + 1$
2	8	$\gamma_{TRC} = 6(8) + 2$
3	11	$\gamma_{TRC} = 8(11) + 3$
4	14	$\gamma_{TRC} = 10(14) + 4$
5	17	$\gamma_{TRC} = 12(17) + 5$
6	20	$\gamma_{TRC} = 14(20) + 6$
7	23	$\gamma_{TRC} = 16(23) + 7$
8	26	$\gamma_{TRC} = 18(26) + 8$
9	29	$\gamma_{TRC} = 20(29) + 9$
10	32	$\gamma_{TRC} = 22(32) + 10$
	.	
	.	
	.	
	.	
n	$n = 3i - 1, i \geq 2$	$\gamma_{TRC} = 2i(3i - 1) + i - 1$

Table 2: Triple connected Roman domination numbers

In each case V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $\langle V_1 \cup V_2 \rangle$ is triple connected.

If $n = 3i - 1, i \geq 2$, then the triple connected Roman domination number founded as

$\gamma_{TRC} = 2i(3i - 1) + i - 1 = 6i^2 - i - 1$

Case (iv): If $n = 6$, then we have $|V_1| = 2, |V_2| = 12, \gamma_{TRC} = 2 + 2(12) = 4(6) + 2 = 26$

Fig. 6: Cartesian product $C_6 \square P_6$ graph

$\Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC} = 26$

Similarly, if $n = 9$, (n will be increased by 3 in each case)

We get $|V_1| = 5, |V_2| = 18, \gamma_{TRC} = 5 + 2(27) = 6(9) + 3 = 57$

For $n = 12$, we have $|V_1| = 8, |V_2| = 48, \gamma_{TRC} = 15 + 2(48) = 8(12) + 4 = 100$

S.No	The value of n	TCRDN
1	6	$\gamma_{TRC} = 4(6) + 2$
2	9	$\gamma_{TRC} = 6(9) + 3$
3	12	$\gamma_{TRC} = 8(12) + 4$
4	15	$\gamma_{TRC} = 10(15) + 5$
5	18	$\gamma_{TRC} = 12(18) + 6$
6	21	$\gamma_{TRC} = 14(21) + 7$
7	24	$\gamma_{TRC} = 16(24) + 8$
8	27	$\gamma_{TRC} = 18(27) + 9$
9	30	$\gamma_{TRC} = 20(30) + 10$
10	33	$\gamma_{TRC} = 22(33) + 11$
	.	
	.	
	.	
	.	
n	$n = 3i, i \geq 2$	$\gamma_{TRC} = 2i(3i) + i - 1$

Table 3: Triple connected Roman domination numbers

In each case V_2 is a dominating set of V_0 and $(V_1 \cup V_2)$ is triple connected.

If $n = 3i, i \geq 2$, then the triple connected Roman domination number is founded as $\gamma_{TRC} = 2i(3i) + i - 1 = 6i^2 + i - 1$

• Theorem

For a Moser spindle graph, the triple connected Roman domination number is

$$\gamma_{TRC}D(T_n) = 5.$$

➤ **Proof:**

Moser spindle graph contains 7 vertices and 11 edges. Here $|V_1| = 1, |V_2| = 2, V_2$ is a dominating set of V_0 and $(V_1 \cup V_2)$ is triple connected.

Hence the function $f = (V_0, V_1, V_2)$ is a triple connected Roman dominating function on G.

So, we have $\gamma_{TRC} = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$

Hence $\gamma_{TRC} = 1 + 2(4) \Rightarrow \gamma_{TRC} = 5$

Fig. 7: Moser spindle graph

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we obtained the triple connected Roman domination number for triangular snake graphs, double triangular snake graphs, Cartesian product $C_n \square P_n$ graph and Moser spindle graph. We will find triple connected Roman domination number for some special graphs such as alternate triangular snake graphs, double alternate triangular snake graphs, quadrilateral snake graph, etc in our future work

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